

The Role of Social Media in the Promotion of Həba (Kilba) Cultural Artistic Practices for Sustainable Development

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Abstract

This study investigates the role of social media in promoting and sustaining the cultural artistic practices of the Həba people in Hong Local Government Area, Adamawa State, Nigeria. It examines how social media is used to source, share, and disseminate information related to cultural values, with a focus on ensuring their transmission to future generations.

Methodology: The research employs a mixed-methods approach, incorporating surveys, primary and secondary data, and visual documentation. This methodology allows for a comprehensive analysis of the impact of social media on the Həba cultural practices.

Findings/Results: The findings indicate that social media serves as a valuable tool in promoting and sustaining Həba traditional practices. It facilitates the wider dissemination of cultural content, helping to maintain and spread Həba artistic expressions and cultural knowledge.

Conclusion: The study concludes that social media has significant potential in preserving and promoting the cultural heritage of the Həba people. However, increased digital literacy within the community is essential for fully harnessing the benefits of social media for cultural preservation.

Recommendations: It is recommended that efforts be made to enhance digital literacy within the Həba community. By doing so, the community can leverage social media more effectively to ensure the continuity and vitality of their artistic traditions for future generations.

Key words: Həba (Kilba) Social Media, Technology, Artistic Practices, Sustainability

Introduction

The emergence of the technological era has ushered in a profound shift in the landscape of communication. Traditional modes of interaction and knowledge acquisition have been significantly transformed by the integration of digital technologies and social media (Buckingham, 2013; Kulesz, 2020; DiMaggio, 2001). This epochal change has manifested in the evolution of communication mediums and materials, enabling the dissemination of socio-cultural information and practices to a global audience with unprecedented reach and speed. Consequently, the boundaries of geographical and cultural limitations have been closed thereby, fostering a more interconnected and interdependent world.

Central to this digital revolution is the phenomenon of social media. Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) conceptualize social media as interactive platforms that facilitate the creation and sharing of user-generated content, underpinned by digital technologies. These platforms have become ubiquitous in contemporary society, serving as primary channels for interpersonal communication, information exchange, and the formation of online communities. The pervasive influence of social media has reshaped various aspects of human life, from personal relationships to political discourse and consumer behaviour. Arijeniwa et al (2022) described social media as;

“a platform where people from their countries upload the material relevant to their culture which includes music, dance, poetry, local food recipes, national games and sports, local events, religious and national events and their celebrations and many other different activities that only exist in specific countries.”

Some of the prevailing social media platforms include Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, Instagram, Tiktok, Snapchat, X among several others. Social media tools are regarded among the fastest growing medium of communication and information dissemination, especially among young people around the world. These social media platforms have also been utilized by individuals and organizations to advertise and promote social events, cultural awareness, businesses and amongst many other uses. Thus, social media could be a significant tool in the promotion and conservation of the cultural heritage of every society for sustainable development.

The cultural artistic practices of the *Haba (Kilba)* people of present-day Adamawa, Northeastern Nigeria has been a significant part of the people’s culture and a definer of their identity. The people are known to practice several unique cultural crafts in weaving, blacksmithing, wood carving, calabash carving and decoration, musical performances, traditional rituals and so forth. However, these cultural practices appear to be losing visibly in

contemporary times, this adversely can pose a threat to the knowledge and sustainability of *Hāba* artistic and cultural practices (Ndonya, 2019, Sharndama, 2021). Leveraging on social media as a tool for the promotion of artistic cultural practices for sustainable development can be thus a great strategy for creating global awareness and sustaining these unique cultural practices amongst the *Hāba* community.

Bitrus (2021), observed that the world is increasingly becoming an information society and that the internet is the brain behind the use of digital social networks in addressing and bridging the gap in awareness creation and communication, especially in the area of digital divide where people lack awareness and information about other cultures, people, practices, about the ill-informed, needy or the deprived people. Baran (2012), in (2010) further posits that, this digital transformation has served as an avenue to bridge the gap between the “have and the have not”, thereby making information available for sourcing, reporting, and reducing the delay in information dissemination.

The promotion of *Hāba* culture and its artistic practices in this digital age would therefore require the instrumentality of social media to share their invaluable cultural practice with the rest of world. By sharing *Hāba* artistic practice on social media foster dialogue, cultural exchange and create awareness and avenues for *Hāba* cultural goods and services to be shared with others. This process can also open doors for technical support and collaboration with the traditional artisans thereby sustaining the cultural practices of the *Hāba* people.

Statement of the Problem

Before the advent of technology, information about cultural and artistic practices took a longer period to reach a wider global audience. Information to and about *Hāba* cultural practices could be hardly accessible, but now with the aid of ICT, it can easily reach a heterogeneous and cosmopolitan audience. The inadequacy of information dissemination of the *Hāba* people has been a setback right from the ancient times, and left many people uninformed about the *Hāba* culture, although the use of social media requires internet accessibility, however, it offers better access to cultural knowledge than before. Thus, with the availability of social media and digital technology, cultural awareness can be transmitted at a faster rate and can reach a wider audience within a short time. It is observed that not much literature and also information about the *Hāba* cultural and artistic practices are available to the global audience on social media.

Additionally, many literatures have been written on the role of social media in cultural education, but at the period of this study no research has been written on the use of social media in the promotion of *Hāba* cultural artistic practices for sustainable development, this understanding hence prompted the researchers to research into this issue, to encourage and promote cultural heritage through the use of technology. This research is also in line with the

United Nations Development Goal number 9.5c which called for the increase access to information and communication technology and the strive to provide universal and affordable access to the internet in least developing countries by 2020. This study therefore would contribute in achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals.

Research Questions

The following are the research questions for this study.

1. What are the roles of social media in the promotion of Həba cultural artistic practices for sustainable Development?
2. What are the most used social media platforms in the promotion of cultural practices?
3. How are social media usage reliable for the promotion and sustainability of cultural artistic practices?
4. What are some of the challenges in the Həba cultural artistic practices?

Literature Review

Role of Social Media in the Promotion of Cultural Artistic Practices

Lunchaprasith and Pasupa, (2021) examined the role of social media in promoting and conserving cultural heritage sites, exploring Hengjia shrine as a case study. The study demonstrates the potential of social media platforms as facilitators of heritage conservation and promotion. The study revealed that social media platforms possess unique capabilities for the immediate diffusion of information to a broad audience, thereby enabling the cultivation of impactful public engagement with heritage conservation efforts and fostering connections between historical narratives and contemporary contexts. In the same vein Liang et al (2021) reviewed the role and impact of social media as platforms for the sustainability of cultural heritage. The study observed that as a result of the increasing need to involve the broader community in the historic urban landscape approach in cultural heritage, social media platforms are thus considered as significant channels in creating awareness and promoting public participation process of urban heritage conservation. The article accentuated that social media provides a platform for the participation of a wider range of stakeholders in the decision process of cultural heritage management. The study therefore recommends that this process should be widely applied in order to encourage global participation in sustainability of cultural heritage.

According to Simplilearn.com (2023), “everyone today is on social media platforms, teenagers on TikTok, influencers and small businesses on Instagram and Facebook, or professionals on LinkedIn, and that social media is always an option that comes to mind” This thus reflect how invaluable social media platforms are, which could be considered as a one-stop platform where

an individual can connect with people across the world, get informed on diverse and current issues on cultural practices, art and entertainment, political affairs, social and technological development. Susanna, (2023), noted that social media has increasingly become an important tool/platform for artists and the art world to showcase their works with the global audience and gain exposure which has resultantly boosted the use of social media platforms like Instagram, Twitter, and Facebook. Additionally, Social media has also brought about significant changes in such a way that art is created, consumed, and valued. In recent times, artists, content creators, bloggers, vloggers and promoters are bypassing traditional gatekeepers, such as galleries, museums, curators, traditional custodians and reach a wider audience on their terms simultaneously.

Reliability of Social Media and Its Challenges in the Promotion of Cultural Artistic Practices

In attempting to ascertain the reliability of social media in the promotion of cultural articles or cultural practices Djumrianti (2018), revealed in his study that Twitter appeared as the most favourite and effective social media platform used to promote and communicate traditional cultural events in Jakarta - Indonesia followed by Instagram and then Facebook. Similarly, Pandia (2018) affirms the instrumentality of the diverse social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, Google+, MySpace, LinkedIn, Pinterest, Snapchat, Tumblr, Twitter, Viber, VK, WeChat, Weibo, Baidu Tieba, and Wikia as very reliable instruments in promoting culture due to the population of subscribers and the advantage of the multifaceted digital elements for global outreach. However, the study of Pandia (2018) further stressed the pros and cons of social media websites on culture, society and education, noting that other researchers have cautioned against leveraging national culture through social media. This observation may be based on the fear of tempering the forms of cultural articles.

Other researchers like Bocar and Jocson (2022) added their concern to Pandia (2018) by observing that whilst social media serve a critical role of offering a platform for creating cultural awareness and transmitting education, however time spent on social media platforms may come with some adverse effects. Bocar and Jocson (2022) noted some of the challenges of social media which may include the occurrence of depression as a result of over-use and the amount of time spent on these social networking websites. Other adverse effects of using social media may include Cyberbullying, undermining other people's cultural practices and lifestyle. Arie Wibowo, et al (2023) further iterated that whilst social media facilitates intercultural exchange and deeper cross-cultural understanding it can also have the potential to create cultural conflict. In view of these adversative effects of using social media, these therefore must be taken into cognizance while using these vital media tools for promoting artistic cultural practices.

According to Statista (2024) out of the 5.44 billion internet users worldwide which amounts to 67.1% of the global population, 5.07 are social media users. These statistics thus infer that 62.6% of the world's population is interacting with one form of social media platform or the other. Following the increasing usage and popularity of social media platforms serves as an indication of its reliability for social and cultural interaction. The web 2.0 on the Internet platform has offered a crucial online community base which according to Xiaoxu Liang; Yanjun Lu and John Martin (2021), has served as a sustainable and holistic heritage conservation to foster an open atmosphere that allows and motivates every user to be involved in the cultural heritage protection through accessing the internet. They further posit that "ICT has played an active role to a broader range of stakeholders' cross scales, classes, races, genders, ages, etc., and are crucial for collaborative planning and conservation."

Social Media today have created an online community which formed a "specific cultural practices or gathered by a common topic based on heritage sites or other forms of cultural heritage, have emerged recently as a result of web 2.0 era" of digitalization compared to that of the physical offline community, where information dissemination of cultural heritage become to difficulties to access even among the *Hāba* community. Wilson & Nuhu (2009), stated that, "the growing digitalization of global activities has left every profession striving for relevance in today's wired world, where professionals have found the use of ICT suitable for use in enhancing practices in their fields of academic endeavour. They further buttressed that "ICTs are generally perceived as the basic tools for survival in modern society."

About the *Hāba* (Kilba) People

The *Hāba* are the indigenous people of Hong Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria. Jival (1993), explained that the *Hāba* people were an integrated union of so many kin ethnic dialects such as the Bura, Babbir, Marghi, Chibok, Hona, Holma, Higgi, Batta, Mbula, Nzanihi, Fali, Ihhi, Kopre and even the Kanuri people of Borno State. The ethnic groups melted and integrated into what is known as the original linguistic stock as the *Hāba* (Kilba) believed to have been the earliest linguistic group that migrated from the North East Africa into the hilly areas of the present-day *Hāba* (Kilba) Community in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The pre-settlement history of the *Hāba* people was only four; the *Pella Gwaja*, *Kulinyi*, *Møkuhi* and Hong mountainous areas. In recent times, the strata of the settlement have now been divided into districts, where the *Hāba* people have seven districts, such as: *Pella Gwaja*, *Kulinyi*, *Gaya*, *Møkuhi*, *Hong*, *Dugwaba*, *Hildi*.

Jival (ibid.p.8) further postulated that, before the present generation, the *Hāba* people had several strata; these settlers could be believed to have immigrated right from prehistoric times. These he said, were the cavemen whose cave drawings and artistic practices such as objects of adornment and potshards were sometimes discovered in the mountains. Some of the artistic practices are still in practice today, especially those that have been used in these texts.

Shardama, (2021), pointed out that, the *Hāba* people were rich in their culture, until the coming of Western education which seriously affected our traditional values, where most of our valuable arts and crafts taught in the curriculum of education were relegated to the Western education. The arts and crafts of cotton spinning and weaving into yarns (*shi pa'oa ana tsa pa'oa*), from which clothes like *gamdu* (traditional gown), *datsu ana sār hindi* (weaved cloth, hang on a thread, tie around the waste, covering only the front private parts and the back side), “Pant”, of today, and is applicable to both men and women then. Some of the arts and crafts are still practiced in the *Hāba* community today, while some are not.

Art and Craft of the *Hāba* People

In the *Hāba* (Kilba) community in Hong Local Government area of Adamawa State, Nigeria, artistic works such as the building of water jars, crafting of wooden seat, mortar, mat weaving, and the designing of calabash, few among others are of great significant.

Gida Biti (Clay Water pot)

Gida Biti (Clay water Pot) is a water container carefully crafted with clay and in some cases fired into terracotta ware. The clay pot is a popular household utensil used by the *Hāba* people before the advent of modern water containers. Despite the advent of modern technology, the clay pot- *Gida Biti* is still being used by some *Hāba* to store water for consumption and other household purposes. The study of Myosein (2023) and Alfakhar, (2023) revealed that using clay pots has some health benefits, citing clay that clay pots improves metabolism, it is gentle on throat, there is absence of toxic chemicals in the water, it can aid curing gastric and acidity problems, it is eco-friendly amongst several others.

Shalla Pəpah (Decorated Calabash)

Shalla pəpah (decorated Calabash), is one of the most popular cultural art artworks of *Hāba*. Calabash decoration is mainly done by women during the dry season after the harvest of farm produce. The calabash is dried a gourd plant, in the family of Cucurbitaceous plants. The rationale behind *Pə shalla* is that when marrying out a daughter, the mother brings out *Shalla Pəpah* from a *Vahl* (Granary) were it is stored, and displays it among the cultural materials such as, *Ber* (traditional Spoon); *Wuləkəu* (saucer carved from Calabash) to dish-out food from a pot after it has been cooked; *Shaku* (Flour Mix Spatula); *Thlafa* (Broom); *Hokhu* (Wooden Seat) and many others.

Nzur-olurdu (mortar)

Mortar and pestle are a pair of grinding tools skillfully carved out of wood great. The Mortar and pestle are among the utilitarian tools that the Həba people use frequently to mix, grind, smash, pulverize, and pound both wet and dry ingredients for use, as such, mortar and pestle are among the oldest tools, and are not limited to kitchen use only, but can also be used in pounding medicine, and other things that needed to be pounded, such

as millet, guinea-corn, among others.

Pəhli

Pəhli, is one of the artworks of the Həba in their community. It is being weaved from Palm leaves, during the dry season, after they are done with the harvest of their farm produce. *Pəhli* is often used for covering of a calabash, spreading of grains when selecting seeds for planting: some of it can be found to be in the shape of Calabash or bowl and can be found in varies designs and colors that one can easily stock

spool thread inside and cover it with its lid.

Theoretical Framework

Ohaja (2003) stated that “knowledge does not exist in vacuum”, thus, every existing phenomenon is understood by some theoretical frameworks. The theoretical framework helps explicate the subject matter under discussion. This study is therefore anchored and understood on the premise of technological determinism theory and cultural production theory.

Technological Determinism theory was propounded by a renowned Canadian Communication researcher, McLuhan (1962), cited by Baran and Davies (2012) stating that “changes in communication technology certainly produce profound changes in both culture and social order.” Adler (2006), conceptualized technological determinism theory as that idea that technology has effects on our lives. This theory in retrospect demonstrates how media technology shapes the thoughts of people, how they feel, act and how the society in general operates.

The bearing of technological determinism theory to this work stems from the fact that social media which is a product of technological inventions has been shown to have enormous impact

on what people know about their immediate artistic cultural practices as well as that of other cultures. This would serve as a means to cultural education and cultural appreciation which ultimately may lead to cultural sustainability.

On the other hand, cultural production theory which hinges on Bourdieu's theory of cultural fields that positions artistic works within the social conditions of their production, circulation and consumption (Bourdieu, 1994). The theory examines all the entities involved in the process of artistic production as well as the individuals and institutions in play. This theory is significant to this study in that its principles served as a perimeter in identifying and discussing the *Hāba* artistic works, their production process as well as their utilitarian and aesthetic functions. Looking at the importance of cultural artistic works which are representations and sign post of a given culture as such, social media can thus be used to promote, educate and sustain such cultural markers and practices.

Methodology

The research strategy adopted for this study is the survey research design. The rationale for adopting the strategy is that it provides a systematic process for collecting data from *Hāba* on their cultural artistic works as well as data on the use of social media in transmitting cultural artistic knowledge. The population of this study is the *Hāba* of Hong Local Government Area 260,900, while the sample size is drawn from the six districts of the *Hāba*, which are *Pella Gwaja, Kulinyi, Gaya, Møkuhi, Hong, Dugwāba*. Krejcie & Morgan sample determination table asserts that for a population of 1,000,000 and above, 120 is appropriate to be a sample size. Questionnaire was used as the instrument for collecting data for this study. 120 questionnaires were administered to respondents through a random sampling technique. In using the random sampling technique Ochoa, (2017) noted that random sampling is used in the selection of samples from the population not because they meet some statistical criterion, but because of their availability to provide useful information.

Data Presentation and Analysis/Results

The following tables indicate data on the category of respondents in this study, social media users, types of social media platforms that can be used in the promotion of cultural artistic practice and artifacts, reliable social media platforms that can be used in promoting cultural heritage, as well as the challenges in the Promotion of Cultural heritage.

Table 1: Category of Respondents by Age

Age Category (n = 120)	Frequency	Percentage
25-30	15	12.5
35-40	26	21.7
45-50	37	30.8
55 and above	42	35
TOTAL	120	100

Source: *Field Survey 2024*

The above data presentation shows that 15(12.5%) category of the respondents were between the ages of 25-30, while, 26(21.7%) were within the age categories of 35-40, furthermore, 37(30.8%) ages range from 45-50 while 42(35%) of the respondents were from the ages of 55 and above. This data therefore shows that 65% of the respondents who are 50 years and below participated in this study. This number is thus significant in that they fall within the range of active social media users.

Table 2: Həba Social Media Users

Do you use social media for the promotion of cultural artistic practices (n = 120)	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	112	93.3
No	8	6.7
TOTAL	120	100

Source: *Field Survey 2024*

Regarding the use of social media by Həba people in learning and promoting Həba artistic practices the results in the table shown above indicate that 112(93.3%) of the respondents were exposed to the use of social media and have used in one form or another in the promotion of cultural artistic practices, while those who are not literate in the use computer and social media stood at, 8(6.7%). These results affirm that there is a huge number (93.3) of young Həba social media users, thus, there are prospects in using social media platforms for the promotion of cultural artistic practices.

Table 3: The Most Used Social Media Platforms in the Promotion of Cultural Artistic Practices.

Types of Social Media (n = 120)	Frequency	Percentage
Facebook	60	50
WhatsApp	51	42.5
Twitter	5	4.2
YouTube	4	3.3
TOTAL	120	100

Source: *Field Survey 2024*

Going by the data in the above table, the most commonly used social media platforms in promoting *Hāba* cultural artistic practices in chronological order are; Facebook, with 60(50%), WhatsApp recorded 51(42.5%), Twitter recorded 5(4.2%), YouTube recorded 4(3.3%). On Facebook, there is a page named Kilba Sons and Daughters with over three thousand followers. The Facebook page is used to showcase and promote diverse *Hāba* cultural activities as well as a networking site for *Hāba* people and the global audience. Similarly, on Instagram, there are the Kilba beautiful faces, YouTube also contains several *Hāba* cultural activities. However, there are several *Hāba* WhatsApp platforms such as the *Hāba* Language Development Association, *Zah* People Forum and many others.

Table 4: Reliability of Social Media Platforms for the Promotion of *Hāba* Cultural Artistic Practices

Reliability of Social Media	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	118	98
No	2	2
TOTAL	120	100

Source: *Field Survey 2024*

In ascertaining the reliability of social media platforms in the promotion of *Hāba* cultural artistic practices 118(98.3%) agree that social media platforms are reliable in promoting cultural activities while 2(1.7%) on the other hand disagree that social media platforms are reliable.

Table 5: Challenges that Affect the Promotion of Cultural Artistic Practices

Challenges of Social Media	Frequency	Percentage
Religion/Western Education	50	41.7
Lack of Modern Equipment	48	40
Lack of Encouragement	10	8.3
Lack of Trained Personnel	12	10
TOTAL	120	100

Source: *Field Survey 2024*

Data in the above table shows responses regarding some of the challenges that affect the promotion of cultural artistic practices; 50(41.7%) of the respondents agree that the presence of foreign religion and Western education are among the factors that can affect the promotion of cultural artistic practices, while 48(40%) cited lack of modern equipment, 10(8.3%) agrees that lack of encouragement, while 12(10%) indicates lack of trained personnel in the handling of modern equipment.

Discussion of Findings

The first findings from the data presented in this study reveals that 65% of the respondents are 50 years and below, this result thus agrees with the data released by Statista (2024) showing that over 85 percent of social media users in Nigeria are under the ages of 55. These data and figures are consequently significant in this study in that they reveal the demography and specific target audience of social media users that contents and knowledge about Həba cultural artistic practices should be designed and targeted towards. In addition, the study reveals a positive use of social media as a tool for the promotion and sustainable cultural practices.

Following the 93.3% of social media users, it is apparent that the vast majority of people on these platforms are literate and tech-savvy to an appreciable level. Additionally, this demography appears to be active user of at least three or more social media platforms and can navigates through their unique interfaces. This information therefore shows that contents and information relating to Həba cultural artistic practices uploaded and transmitted either in video, audio or written formats can be accessed and utilized by the users on any of the earlier listed social media platforms. In support of this, Kavoura and Sylaiou (2019) earlier emphasized the need for cultural organizations and individuals to raise people’s interest and awareness of cultural heritages through cultural contents on technologies and social media which this study seeks to encourage.

The third finding in this study revealed that the most visited social media platform is Facebook with 60%, followed by WhatsApp with 4.2%, YouTube having 4% engagement and Twitter

which is now X with 3% engagement. These results apparently revealed the social media platform that more concentration should be given to (which is Facebook) when developing and pushing social media contents on activities and processes of *Həba* artistic practices. This is not to say other platforms should not be considered as viable platforms, but considering the most visited by a wider audience. Additionally, since few efforts have already been made by individuals and other cultural organizations on Facebook to push cultural contents but not specifically on *Həba* artistic practices, there is therefore the need to create well-structured contents on *Həba* artistic practices,

The efficacy of social media platforms in disseminating cultural artistic practices was a primary focus of this study. An overwhelming majority of respondents (98.3%) affirmed the accessibility, utility, interactivity, and reliability of these platforms for promoting cultural activities. This positive perception is attributed to the platforms' well-structured user interfaces (UI) and user experiences (UX), which facilitate the seamless uploading, management, and dissemination of cultural content. These findings suggest that social media represents a potent tool for sharing and preserving cultural heritage.

The findings of this study align with previous studies by Belch, Belch, and Purrani. (2007), Djumrianti (2018), and Pandia (2018) that underscore the potential of social media as a reliable technological instrument for documenting and transmitting cultural artifacts. However, Pandia (2018) also cautions about the platform's inherent advantages and disadvantages. It is imperative to consider these dualities when developing and sharing content related to *Həba* cultural artistic practices. A nuanced understanding of social media's capabilities and limitations is essential for optimizing its use in preserving and promoting cultural heritage.

Conclusion

This research endeavours to establish a correlation between *Həba* cultural artistic expressions and their dissemination through technological media. By integrating the core tenets of cultural production theory and technological determinism, the study aims to illuminate the ways in which technological social media platforms can be utilized to convey the essence of *Həba* cultural artistic practices. This investigation seeks to understand how these digital tools can effectively capture and communicate the unique characteristics of *Həba* artistic traditions to a broader audience.

The findings of this study thus underscore the potential of social media as a vehicle for transmitting *Həba* cultural education to a global community. By leveraging these platforms, it is anticipated that the study will contribute to preserving and promoting *Həba* culture. This research aligns with the broader objectives and recommendations outlined by Ndonya (2019) and Shardama (2021) regarding the need to integrate, covey and sustain *Həba* cultural artistic

works through technological media. This study thus recommends individuals and Həba cultural organizations leverage and optimize the prevailing and most patronized social media platforms in educating the global audience about Həba cultural artistic practices.

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